

Gender responsive climate smart agriculture practices and its impact on livelihoods of pastoral and agro-pastoral community: A study in Jigjiga, Somali Region, Ethiopia (East Africa).

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Abstract

Although Climate Smart Agriculture Practices are not a new phenomenon in agricultural activities throughout the world but still it is far behind the reaching capacity of people in the African continents in general and the Ethiopia in particular because of many socio-economic and political and cultural factors (for say social standing, awareness, knowledge, gender responsiveness besides economic barriers). Ethiopia is a land locked country having inhabitants of pastoral and agro-pastoral community. Today the environment and climate change has brought new thoughts of doing agriculture practices which can sustain in any climatic conditions in particular region. It needs proper understanding, knowledge in using technology apart from understanding the needs of males and females and their response in practicing Climate smart agriculture (CSA) in order to achieve sustainability in agriculture. Pastoral and agri-pastoral communities mostly are nature lovers, raring livestock –agricultural practices are their life line. Suffering from continuous droughts, untimely rain etc. affects agricultural activities, livestock production which ultimately jeopardized sedentarisation process at large scales among pastoral, agro- pastoral communities in Ethiopia in general and Jigjiga in particular. Finding its ultimate solutions no options remain other than practicing gender responsive climate smart agriculture in the region. This may bring paradigm change not only in

agriculture sector but also integrated sectors in the region where ultimate beneficiaries are pastoral and agro-pastoral communities.

Key words: Climate Smart Agriculture, Pastoral, Agro-pastoral, Ethiopia, Gender responsive

Prelude:

We mean “Gender” normally are two types (i) masculine (ii) feminine through which society has understood sex. It is not insulated to merely men and women. But importance of gender remains a core societal issue since the existence of human kinds. Hence it is traditional reach and value based which takes a new shapes time to time based upon societal needs and values. But gender remains as a source of strength for male and female both irrespective of caste, creeds and culture throughout the world.

Climatic whimsies have a great impact on livelihoods of vulnerable people in the society of a particular geographical location where women and girls may not be exceptional to face the climatic vagaries besides many socio-economic challenges. These challenges ultimately help women to build up capacity using many adaptive techniques that help to find out alternate livelihood options in the way of managing natural resources –agricultural practices in a better way.

Today Climate smart agriculture (CSA) practices become inevitable in such geographic areas where climatic vulnerabilities are more prone to agricultural devastation. Therefore, it encourages the victims particularly the pastoral and agro-pastoral communities to adapt and apply the technologies developed going through policies and programs implement by the state in order to achieve sustainable agricultural development for food security under climate change. It is composed of three main pillars: (1) sustainably increasing agricultural productivity and incomes; (2) adapting and building resilience to climate change; and (3) reducing and/or removing greenhouse gas emissions, where possible through the adoption of a **gender-responsive** approach(World Bank, FAO and IFAD, 2015). This approach means that the particular needs, priorities, and realities of men and women need to be recognized and adequately addressed in the design and application of CSA so that both men and women can equally benefit (World Bank, FAO and IFAD, 2015). It also means that, as changes in

agriculture are pursued in response to a changing climate, there needs to be a consideration of ongoing socio-economic changes.

Pastoralists and agro-pastoralists live their ecclesiastical lives allow nature to lead their lives peacefully . They do not exist either individually or in a homogenous group. The lonely herder wandering in the wilderness to find pasture and water for animals is a romanticized picture of the harsh living and survival conditions of pastoralists (Justin Ginnetti and Travis Franck, 2014). It is estimated that around 120 million pastoralists and agro-pastoralists are living in developing country including in Sub-Saharan Africa. Out of 120 million, it is estimated that around (50million) live in the Sub-Sahara rangelands of Africa in general and East Africa in particularly (FAO,2006). According to study about 12% of the rural populations (Thorntonetal, 2002) are pastoralists and agro -pastoralists and their livelihoods depend upon livestock production , productivity linked with small scale of agriculture. Jigjiga is one among ten woredas in Fafan zone where the majority people are pastoralists and agro-pastoralist. Climatic vagaries have a great effect on their livelihoods. Frequent droughts have become normal phenomenon in this place which made both the gender responsive approach in order to smooth hassle free options to look at alternate livelihoods in their locality. Therefore, gender responsive climate smart agricultural practices definitely will bring a change to facilitate such agricultural practices which are sustainable in nature to find better solution for food insecurity and on the other hand socio-economic growth and development for these vulnerable communities in the study area.

Statement of the Problem

In Ethiopia Pastoralists and agro-pastoralist communities are mostly backward in socially and economically that made them to be marginalized (Hogg , 1997). Changing policies frequently at the interests of majority population of this country ultimately failed to acknowledge pastoralist as a viable way of life (Devereux, 2010). Pastoralists and agro-pastoralists have enough experience to know about climate change because of their high mobility from one to another place for want of suitable livelihoods in country like Ethiopia in general Jigjiga, Somali Region in particular besides fast return rate of drought cycles, and associated uncertainties in the spatial and temporal distribution of water resources and grazing for animals

feeding (Conway and Schipper, 2010). Besides many other Socio-economic factors cultural issues are more sensitive in search of alternative livelihood sources for pastoralists and agro-pastoralists. Therefore, this new agricultural invention giving much importance to gender roles would be a better choice in helping quick sedentarisation process for pastoral and agro-pastoralists in the way of paradigm shifts in the meaning of development today.

Research Questions

The basic research questions that have guided the research endeavor are as indicated below;

- What would be the trend of pastoralists and agro-pastoralists to adopt climate smart agriculture practices?
- What local adaptation strategies do pastoralists and agro-pastoralists follow strengthening gender responsive CSA?
- What are the detriments to do climate smart agriculture practices?

Specific Objectives

- To identify the potentiality of gender responsive CSA among pastoral and agro-pastoral community.
- To examine the strategies are adopted in changing environment for optimal utilization of available resources
- To find the challenges exist for adaptation of gender responsiveness in CSA practices.
- To find the Institutional roles in facilitating gender responsive CSA practices.

Significance and Scope of the Study

This study will provide information on the effective measures to be taken to assess the adaptive strategies of pastoralist and agro-pastoralists in order to make gender responsive CSA practices. In addition, the result of this research will be greatly helpful to development practitioners and policy makers for better understanding about various issues pertaining to this study in order to take proactive roles in near future. This study will also help policy makers to take effective policy actions to encourage such practices so that food security challenges can be met.

Review of Literature

“Men’s lives are shaped by gender (as well as other social factors), their particular constraints or challenges, such as additional stress experienced during times of environmental change” (Lambrou and Nelson, 2009). “a growing body of evidence demonstrates that more equal gender relations within households and communities lead to better agricultural and development outcomes, including increases in farm productivity and improvements in family nutrition” (World Bank, FAO and IFAD, 2015). “A gender-responsive approach will achieve more effective and equitable outcomes, reduce project risks” (Green Climate Fund, 2015). “A participatory approach that identifies income-generating opportunities for women “ (IFAD, 2012, as in FAO, 2013). “Improving their tenure of natural resources, as women’s lack of access to secure land tenure is a major constraint on adopting CSA” (study from Niger and Malawi in World Bank, FAO and IFAD, 2015; Goldstein and Udry, 2008; and Quisumbing and Kumar, 2014). “ In some cases, women have less access to climate information, such as weather forecasts through SMS or radio, in comparison to men” (Twyman, et. al., 2014; Tall, et. al., 2014; FAO, 2013b; Kyazze, et. al., 2012). However, when “women have access to information on CSA, they are often just as likely as men, if not more so, to adopt the practices. (Beddington, et. al., 2012). “An important rationale for investing in CSA is that agricultural growth is the most effective way to reduce poverty and increase food and nutrition security in low-income economies that depend heavily on agriculture—precisely those economies where the majority of the world’s poor and food insecure people live” (World Bank, FAO, and IFAD 2008). There had been many studies in the past but few has addressed this issues ,therefore, researcher has found the research gap in order to undertake this study in Jigjiga Woreda, Fafan Zone, Somali Region, Ethiopia.

Issues

Today food security with having nutritional values are mostly global concerned because of climate vagaries and climate change. The solutions are brought in new agricultural development issues are through climate smart agriculture practices which not only are engaging effectively gender’s potentials but also a sustainable source of household’s income opportunities are found to be an effective approach to reduce poverty and to enhance food and nutrition security. On the other hand climate smart agriculture practices have shown the way of substantial amount of productivity using

optimally the natural resources in general and s land and water are in particular with more efficient and effective way through environmentally sustaining manner (FAO, 2013). In Ethiopia pastoralists are mainly inhabitant in agro- ecology zones like Somali region. Jigjiga Woreda is one among woredas in Somali Region whose 2.51% out of total population of 277,560 are pastoralists and agro-pastoralists (CSA, 2007). These communities are highly tied with traditional values and ethics with patriarchal social structure. It is true that women's contribution towards socio-economic development may be socially ignored most of the time but acknowledged highly by national and global intellects particularly on contribution in agriculture and related activities. FAO's report "on women in agriculture identified that women's contribution to the labor force in production is 43%" (FAO, 2011) as "women face unique challenges in agriculture which negatively impact food security in their homes. These challenges are mainly related to lack of access to resources and opportunities "(Quisumbing et al.2014); power dynamics between family members (Njuki et al. 2016); household roles, and climate change (Quisumbing et al. 2014; Murray et al. 2016). Apart from this if women are deprived off having land ownership rights or other resources that help for efficient production and also to generate income from the sale of agricultural products, there is less food available to satisfy family members 'needs.

Now due to frequent climate change region like Jigjiga is affected by severe droughts (see chart below) has brought new avenue in practicing climate protective, emission free ,well managed natural resources agriculture where gender transformative interventions through gender responsive policy and practice are important. (Morgan 2014). "Women's unique necessities can be considered in these processes which will contribute to reducing the gender gap in agriculture" (FAO, 2011). This will help enormously on easy technology adoption and techniques through reality checks of men and women specific skill and needs among pastoral and agro-pastoral communities in Jigjiga. In this context many studies are found that concentrated about male and female participation in climate smart agriculture using developed technologies which ultimately enhanced women's awareness about technology that shares information about such practices increases among themselves. This attitude has strengthened the resilience of households, communities, and food systems exposed to climate-related shocks and climate change.

Conclusion

Impacts on climate changes are serious today among vulnerability groups like pastoral and agro-pastoralist communities to provide sustainable livelihoods. The key climate change impacts have increased the intensity of natural-hazard induced disasters like continuous rain prolonged droughts etc. though it varies across geographies. Hence frequent changes in climate have adversely impact to the poorest and marginalized segments of society though already they have socio-economic overburdened . Gender based inequalities are in practice. The socio-cultural constraints made women disproportionately vulnerable to climate change. Even though women have proved themselves as change makers through their active engagements in socio-economic activities where agriculture and related activities play pivotal role. Today when the new thoughts have emerged in practicing sustainable agriculture giving due importance of climate change definitely the pastoral and ago-pastoral communities in the Jigjiga region will take the benefits in adapting innovative approaches for surplus agriculture production in the way of gender responsive climate smart agriculture practices. This not only give women's equity but also long term sustainability of their livelihoods through effective management of natural resources keeping in mind sustainable development.

References:

- Ahmad, N., L. et.al, (2014). "Gender, Agriculture, and Climate Change."Agriculture and Environmental Services Note 6. World Bank, Washington, DC. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/2014/02/18967283/gender-agricultureclimate-change>.
- Akande, G., and Y. Diei-Ouadi. (2010). "Post-Harvest Losses in Small-Scale Fisheries: Case Studies in Five Sub-Saharan African Countries." FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper 550. Food and Agriculture Organizationm of the United Nations (FAO), Rome, Italy.
- Alexandratos, N., and J. Bruinsma. (2012). "World Agriculture Towards 2030/2050: The 2012 revision." ESA Working Paper 12-03. FAO, Rome, Italy.
- Agwu. J, Okhimamwe AA. (2009). Gender and Climate Change in Nigeria. Lagos, Nigeria: Heinrich Böll Stiftung (HBS).

Boyd, E. (2002). The Noel Kempff project in Bolivia: gender, power and decision making in climate mitigation. *Gender and Development* 10(2).

Bryan, E, Bernier Q, Espinal M, Ringler C. (2016). Integrating Gender into Climate Change Adaptation Programs: A Research and Capacity Needs Assessment for Sub-Saharan Africa. CCAFS Working Paper no. 163. Copenhagen, Denmark: CGIAR Research Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security (CCAFS).

Blench, R. (2001). You can't go home again: Pastoralism in the new millennium, , Overseas Development Institute, London, UK.

CARE.(2009). Climate Vulnerability and Capacity Analysis Handbook. CARE.

CSA, (2007). National Population Statistics. Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, Central Statistical Authority, Addis Ababa. Ethiopia

Coppock, D.L. (1994). The Borana Plateau of Southern Ethiopia: Synthesis of Pastoral

Cossins, N. J, and Upton,M. (1988a). Options for improvement of the Borana pastoral system. *Agric. Systems* (27) .251-278.

Dreyfus Berhanu, Admassu and Yoseph, Shiferaw (2011).Donkeys, horses and mules-their contribution to people's livelihoods in Ethiopia, The Brooke, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

Desta, S., and Coppock, D.L. (2004) Pastoralism under pressure: Tracking System change in southern Ethiopia. *Human Ecology*, 32(4) 465-486.

Devereux, S. (2006). Vulnerabl Livelihoods in Somali Region, Ethiopia. Research Report

Edmunds D, Sasser J, Wollenberg E. (2013). A gender strategy for pro-poor climate change mitigation. CCAFS Working Paper no. 36. Copenhagen, Denmark: CGIAR Research Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security (CCAFS).

FAO. (2013). Climate-Smart Agriculture Sourcebook. Rome, Italy: FAO. (Available from <http://www.fao.org/docrep/018/i3325e/i3325e00.htm>)

FAO. (2011). The State of Food and Agriculture. Rome, Italy: FAO. (Available from <http://www.fao.org/docrep/013/i2050e/i2050e00.htm>)